

Coupled tropical and polar water vapor variabilities in the lower stratosphere

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Outline

- Coupled circulations in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (UT/LS)
 - Middle and lower atmospheres
 - Polar and tropical atmospheres
 - A review of trace gas (CH_4 and H_2O)
- Forcings and Variations
 - Polar Stratosphere and Upper Atmos: Stratospheric sudden warming (SSW)
 - Tropical Stratosphere: Quasi-Biennial Oscillation (QBO)
 - Tropical Troposphere: El Niño/La Niña-Southern Oscillation (ENSO)
- MLS H_2O in the UT/LS
 - Good tracer
 - Uniform sampling with less impacts from clouds/aerosols
 - Good vertical resolution (~ 1.5 km)

Plumb (2002)

Processes that control the “middle-world” trace gas transport and distribution

- Brewer-Dobson Circulation (BDC)
- Synoptic mixings
- Poleward transport (“pump”)
- Polar subsidence

Are these processes observable?

How are they coupled?

Holton et al. (1995)

CH₄

H₂O

MLS Monthly Mean H₂O

- Horizontal-gradient: necessary for observing poleward transport signatures
- Both moist and dry airs advected to high latitudes
- NH poleward transport seen down to 146 hPa while SH transport down to ~121 hPa
- Poleward transport of moist air: slightly faster in NH than in SH

Tropical Region

- EOF analysis
- Above 100 hPa, ~90% variance from EOF₁
- Above 46 hPa, uniform tropical distribution
- Non-uniform distribution indicating influence from seasonally-and-geographically varying deep convection

Tropical Vertical Ascent

Extratropical Region

- Polar subsidence modulated by SSWs
- Polar H₂O upward progression in UT/LS: a manifestation of poleward transport (i.e., pump) of the moist tropical air
- Eastern Siberia emerging as the key region in the Arctic-bound transport and its variations
- Eastern Siberian anomaly seen in other observations in the lower trop (not shown here)

Extratropical Region

Hemispheric Differences

- Rates of the upward progression similar between in tropics and in NH, as expected for the poleward-transported tropical air
- The SH signature confined in a narrow layer, too shallow to obtain an accurate rate
- Slight increase after 2007 in the NH EOF₁ index?

QBO and ENSO Influences on H₂O Distributions

- Interannual variations from the de-seasoned H₂O series
- Most of the variations originated from the 100 or 121 hPa H₂O variations, which are modulated by QBO and ENSO and mapped out upward and poleward
- QBO (at 121 hPa) and ENSO (at 68 hPa) influences seen in the UT/LS

Summary

- Coupled transports (BDC+poleward) in UTLS studied with Aura MLS H₂O
- Tropics-to-poles and tropo-to-strato gradients in UTLS H₂O: Necessary to observe the transports
- BDC+DeepConv signatures captured by the tropical H₂O EOF₁, showing QBO and ENSO modulations
- Slightly faster NH poleward transport of moist air in UT/LS
- The polar H₂O (mean and EOF₁) upward progression in the LS, indicative of poleward H₂O transport from tropical air
- QBO and ENSO variations in H₂O, mapped out upward and poleward by BDC and the extratropical “pump”